

nccr →
on the move

Attitudes Towards Migration and Democracy in Times of Intertwined Crises

Eva T. Green,
University of Lausanne

Anita Manatschal,
University of Neuchâtel

**Juan M. Falomir
Pichastor,**
University of Geneva

This project examines attitudes toward migration and democracy in the Global North and South in the context of international crises (e.g., COVID-19, climate change, and the rise of anti-democratic norms). Combining the perspectives of social psychology and political science, we use cross-sectional and longitudinal survey data as well as experiments.

Subproject one: bridging recent advances in intergroup research on reactions to emergencies and contextual social psychology, we examine how individual (different facets of identity, intergroup emotions and ideological orientations) and contextual factors (nature of crisis, ideological climates,

structural factors) shape national majority views regarding immigration. We focus on both xenophobia and intergroup solidarity.

Subproject two: recent studies recorded a global erosion in democratic norms and institutions due to populism or political polarization. Expanding on this research, we look at the neglected role of anti-immigrant attitudes. We explore the mechanisms, e.g., how emotions and threat perceptions triggered by crises mediate the link between hostile intergroup attitudes and eroding support for democracy, and examine the role of contextual factors.